

ECONOMIC VIABILITY OF DIFFERENT PLANT POPULATION AND VARIETIES OF LENTIL UNDER EASTERN PART OF VINDHYAN PLATEAU OF MADHYA PRADESH

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Abstract

Different varieties and plant populations influences economic viability in lentil. The present study aimed to productivity and probability of lentil affected by different varieties and plant population. An agronomic investigation was carried out at Department of Agronomy, R.A.K. college of Agriculture, Sehore, Rajmata Vijayaraje Scindia Krishi Vishwa Vidyalaya, Gwalior, Madhya Pradesh during Rabi 2020-21. The experiment laid down in a factorial randomized block design (FRBD) with three replications. The experiments consists of eight treatments combinations i.e. for main factor four varieties RVL31, RVL11-6, RVL13-7, RVL13-5 and sub factor three population density 2.2, 3.3, 4.4, Lakh/ha. Lentil variety RVL13-7 with 3.3 lac/ha were found more remunerative as it fetched maximum gross monetary return (107115 Rs/ha) net monetary return (70178 Rs/ha) and B:C ratio of 2.9. Thus, we can recommended lentil variety RVL13-7 with 3.3 lac/ha to the farmers in Eastern part of Vindhyan Plateau in sub-tropical zone of Madhya Pradesh in a sustainable way.

Key words: Economic viability, lentil, spacing, varieties and yield

Introduction

The lentil (*Lens culinaris* M.) is an important cool season grain legume crop in India, Lentil seeds contain 1-2% fat, 24–32% proteins and minerals (iron, cobalt and iodine) and vitamins. (Whyte *et al.*, 1953). The Lentil (*Lens culinaris* M.) is an important cool season grain legume crop in India, which is second major winter season legume after chickpea. Lentil is an annual plant known for its lens-shaped seed. Lentil is a well-adapted plant that grows in a wide range of soil types. Major lentil growing states like Madhya Pradesh, Bihar and West Bengal. Relatively larger share of lentil production was observed in Madhya Pradesh (30.94%), followed by Uttar Pradesh (28.72%). In Madhya Pradesh it's grown on an 0.56 million ha with the production of 0.64 million tone (Anonymous 2019). Too low and high plant population beyond a certain limit often adversely affects the crop yield. Number of plants per unit area influences plant size, yield components and ultimately the seed yield (Beec and Leach 1989). Optimum plant population density is an important factor to realize the potential yields as it directly affects plant growth and development. The plants are able to fill available space by initiating lateral branches and thus, can compensate for poor emergence and thin stands (Morrison and Muehlbauer, 1986). Optimum spacing can ensure proper growth of the aerial and underground parts of the plant through efficient utilization of solar radiation, nutrients, water, land as well as air spaces. Spacing for line sowing is recommended to maintain the required number of plant population and to undertake intercultural operations for harvesting a higher yield. Seed rate has a major bearing on the yielding ability of any crop. Optimum plant population density is an important factor to realize the potential yields as it directly affects plant growth and development where the plants are widely spaced, biological yields tend to increase linearly with increase in plant density due to no or minimum competition between the adjoining plants and also the higher leaf area index and greater absorption of solar radiation. Thus, the present study Effect of different spacing and varieties on growth and yield of lentil (*Lens culinaris* M.) is proposed to laid out in during Rabi season 2020-21.

Material methods

A field investigation was conducted during rabi season 2020-21 on area having fairly uniform topography, normal fertility status and soil homogeneity at Department of Agronomy, R.A.K. college of Agriculture, Sehore, Rajmata Vijayaraje Scindia Krishi Vishwa Vidyalaya, Gwalior, Madhya Pradesh, which is situated Eastern part of Vindhyan Plateau in sub-tropical zone at the latitude of 23° 12' North and longitude of 77° 05' East at an altitude of 498.77 m from mean sea level (MSL) in Madhya Pradesh. Fig. 1 shows weather parameters during crop season. The experiment laid down in a factorial randomized bloc design (FRBD) with three replications. The experiments consists of eight treatments combinations i.e. for main factor four varieties RVL31, RVL11-6, RVL13-7, RVL13-5 and sub

factor three population density 2.2, 3.3, 4.4, Lakh/ha. Sowing dates of was 16 November 2020. General recommended dose of nutrients were applied through urea and single super phosphate. Complete dose of nitrogen and phosphorus were applied as a basal application. All the recommended package of practices of the zone were followed for growing the crop except varieties and population density. To maintain the healthy crop stand gap-filling at 10 days after sowing (DAS) and thinning at 15 DAS was done in lentil. Lentil harvested at its physiological maturity stage. Pods of each net plot on complete drying were threshed manually and finally winnowed to separate the chaff from the seeds plot wise during both the seasons.

Characteristics of lentil variety RVL 13-7

RVL 13-7 (Raj Vijay Lentil 13-7) is released by RVSKVV, RAK College of Agriculture, Sehore (M.P.). Grain yields of this genotype is 12-15 q/ha with 3.9 g/100 seed index. Maturity period of this variety is 100-110 days. It is also resistant to wilt disease.

Characteristics of lentil variety RVL 31

This variety has been developed from land races of Distt. Shajapur, bold seeded variety with early maturity (107 days). Average yield 1200-1300 kg/ha. Recommended for timely sown rain fed conditions of Madhya Pradesh.

Characteristics of lentil variety RVL 13-5

Suitable for timely sown conditions, average yield 12.4 q/ha, bold seed size (3.9 g/100 seed weight), maturity 106 days, moderately resistant to wilt

Characteristics of lentil variety RVL 11-6

RVL 11-6 is developed by RVSKVV, RAK College of Agriculture, Sehore. It is mainly grown in Madhya Pradesh, Maharashtra, Gujarat, Uttar Pradesh and Rajasthan. Its plant type is semi erect, medium height and branches with broad leaf which is very much suitable for intercropping, average yield 11 – 12 q/ha, maturity 107-113 days. It is also tolerant to wilt.

Cost of cultivation

Cost of cultivation of sole and intercropping system was calculated on the basis of prevailing market price of different inputs like labour, implements, seeds, fertilizers and irrigation, used in cultivation of crops under different grass based cropping systems.

Gross return

The prevailing local market prices were used to convert the yield of lentil into gross return in rupees per hectare.

Net return

Finally economic crop yields were recorded and their monetary returns were calculated on the basis of prevailing market prices of the produce.

Net monetary returns (₹ ha⁻¹) = Gross returns (₹ ha⁻¹) – Cost of cultivation ₹ ha⁻¹)

Benefit: Cost ratio (B: C ratio)

To estimate the benefit obtained from different systems for each

rupee of expenditure incurred B: C ratio of each treatment was calculated as below:

$$B : C \text{ Ratio} = \frac{\text{Gross monetary return (₹ ha}^{-1}\text{)}}{\text{Cost of cultivation (₹ ha}^{-1}\text{)}}$$

Statistical analysis

The data recorded for different parameters were analysed with the help of two factor analysis of variance (ANOVA) for factorial randomized block design (Panse and Sukhatme 1967). The treatment differences were compared at 5% level of significance.

Results and discussion

Highest seed yield was recorded with variety RVL13-7 (13.02 q/ha) and in terms of plant population 3.33 lakh/ha gave (17.32 q/ha) more yield over the control. Our results are in closely agreement with the results of Hamdi *et al.*, 2003, Tripathi and Singh 1987, Rostami *et al.*, 2008 and Eriksmoen *et al.*, 2013).

Cost of cultivation

Cost of cultivation was determined treatment wise on the basis of market price of various common and variable agro-inputs use. It is apparent from the data that treatment P₁V₁, P₁V₂ and P₁V₃ had the lowest cost of cultivation 36337 Rs/ha. The cost of cultivation was further increased varied from Rs 36337 to 37537 Rs/ha in other treatments. The cost was maximum 37537 Rs/ha under P₃V₁, P₃V₂, P₃V₃ treatment and 36937 Rs/ha in P₂V₁, P₂V₂, P₂V₃ and P₂V₄ treatment.

Gross monetary returns

GMR was minimum in combination RVL13-5 with plant population 2.2 lakh/ha (P₁V₄) 36361 Rs/ha, and increases varied from 36361 to 107115 Rs/ha in other treatment. Maximum GMR recorded in P₂V₃ (107115 Rs/ha) and then P₂V₂ 99098 Rs/ha, P₂V₁ 95280 Rs/ha respectively in decreasing order.

Net monetary returns

The net monetary returns (NMR) under each treatment were determined by subtracting the cost of cultivation from GMR of the particular treatment. It was clear from the data that the NMR was Rs. 24 Rs/ha under RVL13-5 with plant population 2.2 lakh/ha (V₄P₁) which is minimum in all the treatment. And NMR are very close in V₂P₁, V₂P₂ and V₃P₂ varied from 6194 to 70178 Rs/ha. And maximum NMR recorded in RVL13-7 with plant population 3.3 lakh/ha (V₃P₂) 70178 Rs/ha. Our results are in closely agreement with the results of Sathyamoorthi *et al.* 2008 who reported that the highest economically profit under plant population of 3.33 lakh/ha.

Benefit - Cost ratio

It refers to net monetary gain under a particular treatment with each rupee of investment. The data on benefit-cost ratio as affected by different treatments have been given in the Table 13 and figure 11. It is evident from the data that B:C ratio was higher under combination of RVL13-7 with plant population 3.3 lakh/ha (V₃P₂) 2.90 closely followed by combination RVL11-6 with plant population 3.3 lakh/ha (V₂P₂) 2.68 and then RVL-31 with plant population 3.3 lakh/ha (V₁P₂) 2.58. Similarly Parveen and Bhuiya, 2010 and Fatemeh Malek

Maleki, 2011 also reported that economically viable in Madhya Pradesh condition.

Conclusion

The combine use of variety V₃ and plant population P₂ was found more remunerative as it fetched maximum gross monetary return (107115 Rs/ ha) net monetary return (70178 Rs/ ha) and B : C ratio of 2.9.

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Table 1 Seed yield of lentil as influenced by different varieties and plant population density

Treatments	Seed yield (q/ha)
Factor A: Varieties	
V ₁ : RVL31	11.58
V ₂ : RVL11-6	12.26
V ₃ : RVL13-7	13.02
V ₄ : RVL13-5	09.34
SE(m)±	0.04
CD at 5%	0.13
Factor B: Population	
P ₁ : 2.2 lac/ha	7.38
P ₂ : 3.3 lac/ha	17.32
P ₃ : 4.4 lac/ha	9.94
SE(m)±	0.03
CD at 5%	0.11

Table 2: Economic analysis of different variety and plant population and variety of lentil

	Cost of cultivation (Rs ha ⁻¹)	Gross returns (Rs ha ⁻¹)	Net returns (Rs ha ⁻¹)	B:C Ratio
P ₁ V ₁	36337	39132	2795	1.08
P ₂ V ₁	36937	95280	58343	2.58
P ₃ V ₁	37537	53668	16131	1.43
P ₁ V ₂	36337	42531	6194	1.17
P ₂ V ₂	36937	99098	62161	2.68
P ₃ V ₂	37537	57266	19729	1.53
P ₁ V ₃	36337	43843	7506	1.21
P ₂ V ₃	36937	107115	70178	2.90
P ₃ V ₃	37537	60353	22816	1.61
P ₁ V ₄	36337	36361	24	1.00
P ₂ V ₄	36937	71496	34559	1.94
P ₃ V ₄	37537	45150	7613	1.20